

P: ISSN No. 0976-8602
E: ISSN No. 2349-9443

RNI No. UPENG/2012/42622

VOL.- XIV , ISSUE- II April - 2025
Asian Resonance

The Role of Working Women in Development of Society : in Reference to Kota City

Paper Id : 19735 Submission Date : 2025-02-07 Acceptance Date : 2025-02-10 Publication Date : 2025-04-02

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15559254

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Abstract India, is growing at a very fast pace with immense growth and development in every field and sectors. we can see growth in science, technology, medicine, healthcare, infrastructural development, educational development, transportation facilities etc. And, thereby the role of women is justified in society. It is a time to acknowledge their contribution and role in family economy and India as a whole. This research paper focuses to study the areas of interest, working hours, and their numbers in various range of economic activities. And, intends to find out the changes in their status in family and society.

Keywords Educational, Fastpace, Interest, Economy.

Introduction

In today's scenario the participation of women in the various economic activities is increasing at a very fast pace. So, the contribution of women being about half of the total populations is to be considered. Once, women participaties in the economy, their empowerment contributes to the society and the productivity levels of the organization has made a marked increase leading to reduction of poverty and increasing the purchasing power capacity of women. Employed women develops high sense of self-esteem and zeal towards life leading to the social upliftment and will bring them out of their homemaker image.

Statement of the Research Problem

The main aim of the study is to identify the role and status of women in the economic development of the society. The study focusses on studying their educational and employment levels in Kota City. Educated employed women has a well defined approach and criteria towards their role is the economic development of the Society.

Objective of study

The purpose of this research paper is to identify the sectors women are employed and amount of time they spend at their workplaces, and calculating their economic contribution and value towards the society making a difference in the development of the society. The calculated difference will help the policymakers to understand the economic contribution of women employees and entrepreneurs and thereby leading to their social upliftment and empower women in real sense.

Mainly, The purpose of the study has been to :

1. To identify the economic activities in which women are engaged.
2. To identify the obstacles that come across in the lives of working women employees that inhibit their progress.
3. To examine the factors which motivate them to get into working mode.
4. To identify the participation rate of women in the various economic activities and their contribution to the family budget and to the economy of the Kota City.
5. To find out the suitable measures to increase the women's contribution in the economy of Kota City.
6. To identify the decisive role of working women in the family.
7. To identify the member of top positions they hold in the organizations driving their empowered approach.

Review of Literature

Dube L. (2001) finds that 'India's patriarchal society thinks of women only as homemakers and sexual objects and is generally subjected to exploitation and torture. Such a reductionist structural attitude would not let women explore their possibilities and discover potentials.

Legal Indian Admin (2010) informs that 'Indian Women still face blatant discrimination at workplaces. A major problem faced by the working women is sexual harassment at workplaces'. Women employees working in night shifts are more vulnerable to such incidents.

Ali, Sophiya (2011) identified the challenges facing women in career development. Most of the women employees are dissatisfied with career development programmes and women are discriminated against in career development opportunities. Top management should also be committed to the career development of women and organizations should also introduce affirmative action to urgently address career development of women. It has been emphasized that advisory board actually discovered that many women were willing to undergo whatever training was necessary to move into management.

Mitra and Mukherjee (2012), conducted a study on one hundred female, adolescent students and their mothers. The tools used were "Perception of satisfaction" from communication with parent scale modified and adopted by **Mukherjee** (1993), adapted version of state trait Anger Expression Inventory and Family Pathology Scale. Underachievers were found to face slightly more family pathology. Achiever's communication satisfaction correlated negatively with both anger expression and family pathology. Family pathology and anger expression were found to be positively correlated. The study revealed that family related problems are crucial for predicting student's achievement. Satisfaction from communication with parent is a positive emotion which equips individual with happiness and better adjustment.

Rakesh K. Chadda and Koushik Sinha Deb (2013) expresses an opinion that unlike the western society, which puts impetus on "individualism", the Indian society is "Collectivistic" in that it promotes interdependence and cooperation, with the family forming the focal point of this social structure. In a situation, where the mental health resource is a scarcity, families form a valuable support system, which could be helpful in management of various stressful situations.

Sabre (2016), investigated the level of marital adjustment among women with reference to their type of family belonging to Madhya Pradesh. For the conduction of study a sample of 120 women (nuclear family = 60 and joint family = 60) was purposively selected. The measure used for data collection was Pramod, K; Kanchana, R. Marital Adjustment scale. The data was analyzed by computing means, SD, t-test. The results revealed that there was a significant difference in marital adjustment among women of nuclear and joint families. The women belonging to nuclear showed higher levels of marital adjustment as compared to women of joint families.

K. Agha, F.T. Azmi, and A. Irfan (2017), in their research study titled "Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction : An Empirical study focusing on Higher Education Teachers in Oman". The objective of study is to measure work-life balance, teaching and job satisfaction of teachers in the higher education institutions in the Sultanate of Oman to explore the relationship between work-life balance, teaching satisfaction and job satisfaction. A total of 1769 teachers from private institutions were contacted, and out of the total of 2717 employees in the government institutions, 1500 could be approached owing to a refusal of certain institutions to participate in the survey. Data was collected from the sample organizations primarily through postal mails, e-mails (2000) and personal visits (1269). The mail methodology has also been used by other researchers in this area of study. Findings of the study revealed that while work interference with personal life and personal life interference with work had a negative relationship with job satisfaction, work and personal life enhancement had a positive relationship with job satisfaction. Thus, the findings of the present study corroborate with previous research evidence. Thus, we can safely conclude that work and personal life needs to be integrated and balanced by organizations through work-life balance initiatives.

Rakesh Belwal, Shweta Belwal (2017), in their study titled, "Employers' perception of women workers in Oman and the challenges they face." The aim of this study is the participation and productivity of women in Oman's labor force are very low and heavily skewed toward the government sector. There are few women in the private sector and the reasons for this are not well-known. Data collected by interviewing the top executives (employers) from 28 organizations in two face. This study synthesized and grouped employer's perceptions of these challenges in the following categories: Women's natural

and physiological composition, their attitude at work, post-marital challenges, socio-cultural barriers, nature and place of work, organizational preparedness and governance, biases or prejudices of employers, and work-life balance (WLB) issues facing them.

Kakul Agha (2019), in her study titled "Work life Balance among Teachers Employed in Higher Education in Oman : Emerging Issues & Challenges". This study focuses on the work life balance issues of the university teachers and contextual factors. It has attempted to capture work life balance among the university teachers and contextual factors. It has attempted to capture work life balance among the university teachers across the Sultanate, and finds out the impact of the difference in gender, nationality Omani or non-Omani, private or public sector institution. The study consists of a cross sectional design, the data was collected from 621 teachers employed across Omani higher educational institutions based in Muscat and other cities in the Sultanate. The research shows that significant differences lie among genders, nationalities and place at work. Also, work practices need to be managed in the correct way to create an efficacy of Work Life Balance program.

Dr. G. Balamurugan, M. Sreeleka (2020), in there study titled "a study on work life balance of women employees in it sector", the purpose is how the women employees are balanced and Satisfied in IT sector and the factors that affect the work life balance of women employees are working hours, Job satisfaction, working condition, etc. and find out the women employee job satisfaction were analyzed by using statistic al method that is Chisquare and Correlation test. The primary data were collected technique used was purposive quota sampling. The findings of the study can justify its utility since knowing the faculty members precisely and reaching out to them in the effective way, is the key to minimize stress.

Laxmi Devi Sharma & Nisha (2021), in their study titled "WORK-LIFE BALANCE : A LITERATURE REVIEW", The aim of the paper is to understand firstly the concept of work-life balance, the effect of work-life balance in various professions mainly focusing on education sector and also to know the influence of work-life imbalance on the well-being of the teachers. The study reviews literature from articles, book, journals, conference proceedings etc. It has been tried to find out the concepts and areas where studies were reviewed on work-life balance and its future scope for research. They found the proper balance between work and personal life help in attaining both organizational and personal goals. The work-life imbalance affects negatively both professional and personal life, leading to decrease in the profuctivity of the employees. The work-life balance has become an issue both in manufacturing and academics' sector. The teachers are also facing the problem of work-life imbalance.

Dr. Ahmed M. Asfahani (2021), in his study titled "Work-life Balance and Role Conflict among Academic Staff in the Middle East", The main aim of this research was to find balance between work and life. An imbalance in the work-family relationship can cause health problems and decrease performance outcomes at work. The information for this study was collected from post studies and reviews on WLB and Role Conflict among academicians from Middle East. This study finds out, the levels of work-life balance and role conflict vary with culture. The change in levels is influenced by gender equality, individualism/collectivism, and the power distance dimension of culture.

Methodology

Study Area

The present study was conducted in Kota city of Rajasthan. The city known for its educational and industrial stature in the state. It is located 240 kilometers south of the state capital, Jaipur situated on the banks of Chambal River. The city known for the production of millet, wheat, rice, pulses, coriander, oilseed milling, distilling dairying, textile weaving, manufacture of metal handicrafts, fertilizer, chemicals and engineering equipment. It has an extensive industry of stone-polishing of a stone called Kota stone. Kota has mainly three types of climatic seasons i.e. long and dry summers from end of March to the end of June. The monsoon season has low tempratures, but highly humid. The winter starts in late November and lasts to the end of February month.

Scope of the Study : This research study focusses to find out the numerous sectors in which women are employed in Kota city. This study will help in throwing light upon the problems they face at home and workplaces particularly. This study will provide a data of employed class among women in Kota city. Their count and economic contribution in family and society at large will influence the policy makers to formulate motivating and supportive policies and programmes for working women.

Collection of Data :Th study of the universe consists of all the women engaged in major economic activities in Kota city of Rajasthan state. The respondents taken were 640 in

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VOL.- XIV , ISSUE- II April - 2025
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total from Kota North and Kota South Municipal Corporation on the basis of Population. Area and literacy rate of the ward with the help of stratified random sampling method. The data was collected from Govt. Schools, Govt. Offices, Bank and Private Schools.

Sampling

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Women are contributors in economic growth. The present study tries to formulate detailed profile of women employees in Kota city. The sample comprises of 640 women working in Kota city. In the study, name, age, marital status, monthly income, family type, qualification, number of children, preference to do job, current job status and their opinion about the sector which is good for women with respect to job is considered.

Table 1 : Frequency distribution of Age of women participants

Age	Type of Organization				
	Govt. School	Govt. Office	Bank	Pvt. School	Total
15-25	80	78	69	60	287
26-36	36	68	48	77	229
37-47	26	09	10	08	53
Above 48	18	05	33	15	71
Total	160	160	160	160	340

Source : Field Survey year 2021

Frequency Distribution of Age of Women Participants

Table 2 : Frequency Distribution of marital Status of women participants

Marital Status	Govt. Office	Govt. School	Bank	Pvt. School	Total
Unmarried	95	83	67	90	335
Married	63	64	78	67	272
Widow	01	06	13	03	23
Others	01	07	02	0	10
Total	160	160	160	160	640

Source : Field Survey year 2021

Frequency Distribution of Marital Status of Women Participants

Table 3 : Frequency Distribution of Monthly income of Women Participants

Type of Organization					
Monthly Salary	Govt. School	Govt. Office	Bank	Pvt. School	Total
Less than 15000	04	08	10	17	39
15001 to 25000	50	55	78	72	255
25001 to 35000	95	35	52	42	224

Above 35000	11	62	20	29	122
Total	160	160	160	160	640

Source : Field Survey year 2021

Frequency Distribution of Monthly income of Women Participants

Table 4 : Frequency Distribution of women's participants opinion for the sector good

for women.

Type of Organization					
Women Friendly organization	Govt. School	Govt. Offices	Bank	Pvt. School	Total
Too great extent	28	40	74	65	207
To some extent	95	109	36	84	324
Limited extent	35	05	20	10	70
Not at all	02	06	30	01	39
Total	160	160	160	160	640

Source : Field Survey year 2021

Frequency Distribution of women's participants Opinion for the sector good for women

Table 5 : Frequency Distribution of Qualification level of Women Participants

Qualification	Type of Organization				
	Govt. School	Govt. Office	Bank	Pvt. School	Total
Up to 12th	05	0	15	40	60
Graduation	104	16	80	72	272
Vocational Degree	45	143	26	25	239
Others	06	01	39	23	69
Total	160	160	160	160	640

Source : Field Survey year 2021

Frequency Distribution of Qualification level of Women Participants

Frequency distribution of Number of Children of Women Participants

In the current scenario, there is a two child norm and there are 310 respondents with single child and 250 respondents had two children and the rest 80 respondents did not had a child. It is perceived that working women has to put lot of efforts in raising their children. So, they avoid taking chances and it is a biggest constraint leading to stress.

Frequency distribution of working sectors of women participant.

The women participants were mainly employed in education sector, health sector, account sector and rest in other sectors being self employed and majority of the respondents in govt. sector jobs in primary education sector.

Frequency Distribution of preferred sector for job of women participants

The participants were asked questions regarding the preferred job sectors for women participants. The preferred answers in majority were for education, health and self employed category.

Tools Used The instruments used in the research and questionnaire and schedule.
Pearson's Chi-square test is used to test the hypothesis.

Analysis

In the research study, women were asked several questions to identify the role of women in the economic world. Questionnaire method was adopted to find the opinion of women employees. Use of five point likert scale was used. Statistical analysis such as cronbach's Reliability test has been used to check the reliability of the data. The relationship between demographic characteristics of participants and their preference for a particular job and willingness to do a job. Analysis of the motivating factors and reasons for being in a job, analysis of satisfaction for job, problems faced by women at workplace, role of women in family economy, use of women salaries for different types of work, analyze the impact of working women on the status of the family, to study the role of women in the economic development has been studied and examined in this research paper.

Conclusion

Kota is a flourishing city in terms of education and industrial base. Therefore, The city has generated numerous economic activities in various sectors. The main purpose of the study is to examine the participation rate of women in the economic activities and their contribution to the family budget and economy of the city and sends a message to the policymakers to enhance the women's participation in the economy of the Kota city. In this research study, 640 working women were chosen on the basis of stratified random sampling method. In the present study, the different economic activities defined were self-employed, account workers, microenterprise, Govt. jobs, private jobs, semi govt. jobs. Secondary database has been collected through various sources such as websites, Journals etc.

Limitation of the Study The present study has some limitations. The question asked related to monthly salary, problems of women at workplaces, their decisive roles in the organizations were not answered promptly by the respondents. Questions related to sexual exploitation at workplaces, security and sanitation were very crucial to deal with.

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P: ISSN No. 0976-8602
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RNI No. UPENG/2012/42622

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